

HELIOPHYSICS BIG YEAR

National Aeronautics and
Space Administration

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HELIOPHYSICS

Heliophysics is the study of how our own star, the Sun, affects our lives on Earth and the whole solar system. The Sun gives us light and warmth, which helps plants grow and provides food for us all. It is like a big clock that guides us through the rhythms of day and night, the seasons every year, and cycles of the universe that last for billions of years!

SAFETY INFORMATION

When viewing the Sun with solar viewing glasses, only take the glasses off during the brief moments of totality.

Looking directly at the Sun without proper eye protection is unsafe except during the brief total phase of a solar eclipse ("totality"), when the Moon entirely blocks the Sun's bright face, which will happen only within the narrow path of totality.

A total solar eclipse is about as bright as a full Moon — and just as safe to look at. But the Sun at any other time is dangerously bright. View it only through special-purpose solar filters that comply with the transmittance requirements of the ISO 12312-2 international standard for filters for direct solar viewing.

Credit: AAS

SEE INSIDE COVER FOR ECLIPSE ACTIVITIES.

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Raven Steals the Sun,” is an artist’s depiction inspired by the traditional Tlingit story “How Raven Stole the Sun” by Maria Williams. Illustration by Hannah Foss, Geophysical Institute, UA, © 2023, University of Alaska Fairbanks (used with permission).

Geometry of a Total Solar Eclipse

A solar eclipse occurs when the Moon casts a shadow on Earth's surface. To see a total solar eclipse, you must observe it from the inner part of the shadow, the umbra. Those observing from the outer part of the shadow, the penumbra, experience a partial solar eclipse.

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